

Studies on ternary complexes of nickel(II) involving ligands with nitrogen, sulfur or oxygen as donor groups

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Analysis of the pH-titration data in the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane/1,3-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid(B) systems show the presence of NiAB ternary species in addition to the binary species HA, H₂A, NiAH, NiA, NiA₂H, NiA₂, NiA₃, HB, H₂B, H₃B, NiB, NiB₂H and NiB₂. The coordination of ligands A and B in both the binary and ternary complex species are similar and the ternary species tetracoordinated. The NiAB species have a square-planar structure.

Investigations on the complex forming properties and important chemical reaction of naturally occurring amino acids, L-cysteine and D-penicillamine have been carried out by several workers¹. The complex chemical equilibria of both L-cysteine and D-penicillamine are determined by the mercapto sulfur donor atom which is soft in character. These compounds participate in both redox and acid-base reactions through the mercapto group. A study of interaction of Cu^{II} with these ligands is highly complicated because the complex formation and redox reaction take place simultaneously². A deeper understanding of this type of chemical reaction requires the extension of investigation to complexes of other transition metal ions such as Ni^{II}. Only few reports^{3,4} are available in literature on the systematic investigation of ternary complexes involving sulfur containing ligands, such as L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid. In this paper the results obtained on the complex forming properties of 1,2-diaminopropane and 1,3-diaminopropane with Ni^{II} in presence of the sulfur containing ligands L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid are reported.

Results and Discussion

The log K_{NiAB}^{NiB} values of 6.58, 6.06 and 5.86 obtained respectively in the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) systems are comparable to the log K_{NiA}^{NiA} value in the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane binary system (Table 1). This shows that 1,2-diaminopropane ligand binds the metal ion in a bidentate manner via two amino groups leading to the formation of one five-membered chelate ring. The log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} values of 8.77, 10.61, 4.84 obtained in Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) systems compare favourably with the log K_{NiB}^{NiB} values respectively in the Ni^{II}-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) binary systems. This shows that the binding mode of L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid ligands in their NiAB mixed ligand species is similar to its binding in the corresponding NiA binary species⁴, i.e. L-cysteine and D-penicillamine ligands bind via *N*-amino and *S*-sulfhydryl groups and L-cysteic acid binds in a glycine-like mode also

Table 1 Stability constants for the Ni^{II} complexes of 1,2-diaminopropane, 1,3-diaminopropane, L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid*

Parameter	Temp = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄)				
	1,2-Diamino- propane ^a	1,3-Diamino- propane ^a	L-Cysteine ^b	D-Penicill- amine ^b	L-Cysteic acid ^b
log β _{HA}	9.80(8)	9.99(8)	10.31(2)	10.89(1)	8.41(1)
log β _{H₂A}	17.01(9)	18.31(9)	18.53(7)	18.89(5)	15.56(4)
log β _{H₃A}			19.93(8)	20.80(9)	
log β _{NiAH}	12.29(7)	13.45(9)			
log β _{NiA}	6.95(3)	5.96(7)	9.14(9)	11.50(3)	5.93(4)
log β _{NiA₂H}	18.89(9)		25.86(9)		
log β _{NiA₂}	13.07(3)	11.28(9)	20.21(5)	23.41(1)	10.53(6)
log β _{NiA₃}	17.13(1)				

*Ligands, L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid become ligand B in the ternary systems

^aRef 13, ^bRef 8

Table 2. Stability constants for the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid(B) ternary systems

Temp = 37°, I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄)

Parameter	1,2-Diaminopropane(A) ligand system ligand, B			1,3-Diaminopropane(A) ligand system ligand, B		
	L-Cysteine	D-Penicillamine	L-Cysteic acid	L-Cysteine	D-Penicillamine	L-Cysteic acid
log β _{NiAB}	15.72(5)	17.56(9)	11.79(2)	14.64(8)	16.75(11)	10.92(2)
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiA}	8.77	10.61	4.84	8.68	10.79	4.96
log K _{NiAB} ^{NiB}	6.58	6.06	5.86	5.50	5.25	4.99
Δlog K _{NiAB}	-0.37	-0.89	-1.09	-0.46	-0.71	-0.97

in the NiAB ternary species resulting in the formation of a five-membered chelate ring. Thus NiAB species in Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) systems would contain two five-membered chelate rings.

The parameter Δlog K_{NiAB} = (log β_{NiAB} - log K_{NiA}^{Ni} - log K_{NiB}^{Ni}) has been calculated and all these values are less negative (Table 2), indicating marked stability for NiAB ternary species compared to NiA or NiB binary species⁵. The NiAB species has been found to occur more than 50% of the total metal ion in all the systems. The diagram obtained for Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-D-penicillamine(B) system is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-D-penicillamine(B) system at a Ni-A-B ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 (C_M = C_A = C_B = 0.003). Curve for NiA₃ could not be drawn because of its very low concentration. (1) Unbound Ni^{II}, (2) NiAH, (3) NiA, (4) NiA₂H, (5) NiA₂, (6) NiB, (7) NiB₂ and (8) NiAB.

The following conclusions can be arrived at in the cases of Ni^{II}-1,3-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) ternary systems. (i) The comparable log K_{NiAB}^{NiB} values in the above three ternary systems (Table 2) with the log K_{NiA}^{Ni} value in the Ni^{II}-1,3-diaminopropane (A) system (Table 1) show that in the NiAB species, 1,3-diaminopropane binds the metal ion via two amino groups resulting in the formation of one six-membered chelate

ring. (ii) The log K_{NiAB}^{NiA} values in all the systems bear favorable comparison with the respective log K_{NiB}^{Ni} values (Tables 1 and 2). This shows that the binding of L-cysteine, D-penicillamine and L-cysteic acid are same in the NiAB ternary and NiB binary species, i.e. L-cysteine and D-penicillamine bind in a bidentate manner via N-amino and S-sulfhydryl groups, and L-cysteic acid binds in a glycine-like mode resulting in the formation of a five-membered chelate. Thus, NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-1,3-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine, -D-penicillamine and -L-cysteic acid(B) systems would contain six- and five-membered chelate rings. (iii) The Δlog K_{NiAB} computed⁵ in all the three systems are less negative, indicating marked stability for NiAB ternary species compared to the binary analogs. In all these three systems more than 50% of the total metal ion has been found to be in the form of NiAB species.

As a representative case, the electronic absorption spectrum for the NiAB species in the Ni^{II}-1,2-diaminopropane(A)-L-cysteine(B) system was recorded. The observed λ_{max} value (480 nm) shows that the NiAB complex in this system would have a square-planar geometry with transition ³A_{1g} → ³B_{1g}. In case this species would have a tetrahedral geometry⁹, then the λ_{max} value would be 500–700 nm. Thus, it can be expected that the NiAB species in all the six title ternary systems would have a square-planar geometry.

Experimental

All the ligands used were Fluka products of puriss quality. Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions. The method of preparation and determination of nickel perchlorate and other reagents have been described earlier^{6,7}. The pH-titrations were done on solutions with the total concentration of metal, ligand A and ligand B in 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 : 2 ratios at 37° under nitrogen atmosphere using a pH meter (Electronic Corporation of India Ltd.; accuracy = ±0.01). A constant ionic strength of 0.15 mol dm⁻³ was maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate. All the calculations were done with the aid of MINUQUAD-75 computer program⁸ on a CYBER 180/830 A

Note

computer, fixing the acid dissociation constants of the ligands and parent binary constants estimated under identical conditions (Table 1). The ternary species of stoichiometry NiABH₂, NiABH and NiAB have been assumed in different chemical models during computation. However, only NiAB species was detected in all the systems (Table 2). Electronic spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B spectrophotometer. For recording the spectra 1 : 1 : 1 metal, ligand A and ligand B solutions were used at a particular pH where NiAB species was found in maximum concentration as shown by species distribution diagram.

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